

Comparative Characterisation of Activated Carbon from Nigerian Sub-bituminous Coal, Palm Kernel Shell and Cow Bone

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Activated carbon consumed in Nigeria is imported from British Drug House, United Kingdom. The purpose of this investigation is to determine how effectively locally produced activated carbons substitute for the imported variety as a decolourising agent.

For this investigation, carbonisation was carried out by heating Nigerian sub-bituminous coal at 550° ¹, palm kernel shell at 650° ² and cow bone at 800° ³ in the absence of air. Activation was carried out by heating the carbon with orthophosphoric acid.

Equal weights of the activated carbons, including imported activated carbon for comparison, were used to decolourise the same volume and concentration of pink coloured KMnO_4 solution. The extent of decolourisation was assessed and compared by visible light absorbance measurements on the decolourised solutions. Factors which could influence the decolourising power of activated carbons include their percent fixed carbon and specific surface area.

The percent ash content and hence the percent fixed carbon, of each activated carbon was determined. The specific surface area was determined using the method of absorption of paranitrophenol (PNP) in aqueous solution following the reported procedure⁴. Because of the importance of porosity to the surface area of solid absorbents, the micropore volume of each activated carbon was determined using the mercury porosimeter following the reported method⁵.

Results and Discussion

Table 1 presents the visible light absorbance tests on the decolourised KMnO_4 solutions by the various activated carbons, as well as the percent ash and fixed carbon content, the specific surface area, and the aircropore volume of the activated carbons. The Table also shows the percentage residual colour of the $0.2M$ KMnO_4 solution after decolourisation, computed based on the absorbance.

Visual observation showed that all four active carbons decolourised KMnO_4 solution. Light absorbance measurements showed that the degree of decolourisation varied among the active carbons. Activated carbon from cow bone exhibited equal decolourising power as the imported variety. These two are followed by activated carbon from palm kernel shell. Activated carbon from Nigerian sub-bituminous coal decolourised least.

The percent fixed carbon is lowest in activated carbon from the sub-bituminous coal which exhibited the minimum decolourising ability. But the fixed carbon contents of the activated carbon from palm kernel shell, cow bone and the imported variety, are identical, whereas their decolourising powers vary. This indicates that the fixed carbon content, though it may be of importance, is not the principal de-termining factor of decolourising power.

The imported activated carbon and active carbon from cow bone, which exhibited the highest decolourising power, have the highest micropore volumes and the

TABLE I—ABSORBANCE, ASH, FIXED CARBON, SPECIFIC SURFACE AREA AND MICROPORE VOLUMES OF THE ACTIVATED CARBONS

Activated carbon from	Absorbance at 600 nm	% Residual colour	% Ash in activated carbon	% Fixed carbon in activated carbon	Specific surface area $\times 10^6$ m ² /ton	Micropore volume m ³ /ton
Nigerian sub-bituminous coal	0.035	29.2	25.26	74.74	410	0.18
Palm kernel shell	0.018	15.0	4.49	95.51	650	0.31
Cow bone	0.008	6.7	4.36	95.64	847	0.48
Imported from BDH	0.007	5.8	3.26	96.74	850	0.49
Distilled water	0.00	0.0				
0.2 M KMnO ₄	0.12	100.0				

highest specific surface areas. Porosity and specific surface fell from these two to activated carbon from palm kernel shell and sub-bituminous coal which exhibited lower decolourising power. Among these less decolourising carbons, active carbon from palm kernel shell has a higher micropore volume and specific surface area, and decolourised better than active carbon from the sub-bituminous coal. The porosity and specific surface of activated carbon are thus the principal factors that determine the ability and extent of decolourisation.

Conclusion : Activated carbon from cow bone and palm kernel shell function efficiently as decolourising agent. Active carbon from Nigeria sub-bituminous coal is a low grade decolourising agent, having a high percentage residual colour. Active carbon from cow bone is the most efficient, being of the same level of efficiency as the imported variety. Decolourising power increased with increasing micropore volume and specific surface area.

Experimental

Carbonisation was carried out by heating the sample in a muffle furnace earlier deaerated with nitrogen gas. The carbon obtained was pulverised to 100 percent minus 200 mesh BS (75 μ m) to

correspond to the size of grind of the imported active carbon.

Activation was carried out in a steel U-tube. The mixture was carbon + orthophosphoric acid (1 : 2, w/v) and was heated at 900^o for 1 h.

Absorption spectrophotometric tests were carried out at 600 nm using a Spectronic 20 spectrophotometer. Absorbance readings were obtained to a reproducibility of $\pm 1\%$.

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